

Studies on Thorium Anthranilate

Y. H. Deshpande and V. Ramachandra Rao

A new complex compound of thorium with the bidentate ligand anthranilic acid has been prepared. Its absorption spectra in the ultraviolet, visible and infrared region have been recorded. It was found that the Th^{4+} ion is attached to four molecules of the ligand.

Anthranilic acid has been reported as a gravimetric reagent for thorium¹. It has been reported that the thorium anthranilate obtained has the composition $(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2\text{Th}(\text{OH})_2$ ². In an attempt to study the comparative behaviour of several reagents for estimation of thorium which were already reported, anthranilic acid was chosen and its thorium complex prepared. Its composition, ultraviolet, visible and infrared spectra are reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

The absorption spectra in the ultraviolet and visible region were recorded using a Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. The infrared spectrum was recorded on a Perkin Elmer model 137 infracord. Anthranilic acid was of reagent quality and it was recrystallised before use from hot water (m.p. 145°).

Preparation of the Chelate : To a solution of thorium nitrate in ethanol (obtained from a weighed amount of thorium oxide (99% pure) in A.R. nitric acid), a calculated amount of the ligand (mole ratio 1 : 4) in ethanol was added. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.0 with alcoholic ammonia and the solution was refluxed on a steam bath for 1 hr. The contents were cooled and concentrated on a steam bath when the solid complex separated. The solid was washed with acetone and vacuum dried for 48 hrs over fused calcium chloride. It was found that (a weighed amount of the dried chelate was ignited in a platinum crucible and the residual oxide weighed) the metal to ligand ratio was 1 : 4. (Found metal 29.59%, Th $(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_4$ requires Th, 29.70%). The conductivity data of the complex in methanol indicated that the complex is a non-electrolyte.

Spectral data : The absorption spectra of anthranilic acid and its metal chelates in the ultraviolet region were recorded by Hill and Curran³. They observed a maxima at 320 $m\mu$ in the solvent ethanol for the free ligand and this was shifted to shorter wave lengths on chelation. In this investigation it was noticed that the ligand has shown two absorption

1. D. I. Ryabchikov and E. K. Golbraikh, *The Analytical Chemistry of Thorium*, Pergamon Press, 1963, page 56.
2. D. S. N. Murty and Bh. S. V. Raghava Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **27**, 459.
3. A. G. Hill and C. Curran, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 1519.

maxima, one at $335\text{ m}\mu$ ($\epsilon = 4559$) and the other at $245\text{ m}\mu$ ($\epsilon = 7580$) in methanol. In the thorium chelate the $335\text{ m}\mu$ band of the ligand is shifted to $330\text{ m}\mu$ ($\epsilon = 15470$) whereas there is no shift in the $245\text{ m}\mu$ band ($\epsilon = 25950$).

In the visible region the ligand and the Th^{4+} ion do not have any absorption maxima and as such no absorption maxima is located in this region in the complex. The infrared spectra of some salts and metal chelates of anthranilic acid have been reported³.

It has been demonstrated that coordination of the amino group with metals results in an appreciable decrease in the frequencies of N-H stretching vibrations. In the case of Mg(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) anthranilates there is a shift to lower frequencies of the order of $149\text{--}187\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In our investigation a band is located in the ligand at 3450 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the N-H stretch frequency of the amino group. In the thorium complex a band at 3325 cm^{-1} is located and this could be assigned to the N-H stretch frequency and the order of shift to a lower frequency is about 125 cm^{-1} . So evidently one could postulate the formation of N \rightarrow M dative bond.

In the free ligand four bands are located in the $1620\text{--}1520\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. But whereas in the thorium complex only three bands are located at 1635 , 1570 and 1510 cm^{-1} . Hill and Curran have also observed three peaks in the anthranilates of Mg(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) and have attributed the two high frequency peaks to the C = C ring vibration and the third strong one to the asymmetric COO^- stretching vibration (with probably some contribution from third ring vibration). The 1635 and 1570 cm^{-1} bands obtained in the thorium complex could be assigned to the C = C ring vibration and that at 1510 cm^{-1} is due to asymmetric COO^- stretching vibration. Hill and Curran³ have compared the spectra of the esters and chelates of anthranilic acid and observed that there is a large shift of the bands in the above region on esterification, whereas upon chelation the shifts are small. They concluded from this that in anthranilate complexes the $\text{COO}^- \cdots \cdots \text{M}^+$ bond is essentially electrostatic in nature. In the thorium anthranilate also it is noted that the shifts in these bands are small on chelation and one could infer that the $\text{COO}^- \cdots \text{M}^+$ bond could also be electrostatic in nature in the thorium anthranilate.

The authors are grateful to Prof. D. D. Khanolkar for his interest and encouragement. They also express their gratitude to Prof. N. V. Subba Rao for the facility given to them to record the infra-red spectra.